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STRATEGIC PROSPECTS FOR THE DEVELOPMENT OF THE TOURIST SERVICES MARKET IN UKRAINE

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Abstract

The article analyzes the theoretical foundations and features of the strategic development of the tourist services market in Ukraine. The concept of the tourist services market is comprehended and revealed. The methodological approach of strategic development of the tourist services market in Ukraine and the specifics of recovery after the coronavirus pandemic are highlighted. The priority tasks of the tourism industry development in Ukraine are presented and argued. The model of the strategic management process in tourism for a tourist enterprise is generalized. The algorithm of development of the competitiveness extension project of the tourist services market in Ukraine has been elaborated and substantiated. The conclusion is substantiated that in order to ensure a stable growth rate of the tourism industry, it is necessary to identify priority types of tourism for the regions, contribute to improving the safety of tourists, develop tourism infrastructure and transport links, simplify formalities, create and sell tourism products and services that are in demand on the world market, develop and rapidly introduce new technologies using digital tools.

Keywords: tourism industry; tourist services market; competitiveness; innovations; tourist resources; tourist services; strategic development of the tourist services market; marketing technologies; effective management

Introduction

The market of tourist services, as a complex economic sector of Ukraine, has the highest degree of flexibility of natural, general economic, social and political changes in the country. The complexity of the situation in the tourism sector in Ukraine is that it is negatively affected by systemic factors, mega, macro and meso environments, which are unpredictable in nature. Convinced that in order to reduce the impact of negative factors on the market of tourist services it is necessary to constantly monitor the development of the tourist environment of this sector, conduct marketing research to change geospatial vector tourist routes to respond quickly to meet effective consumer demand, fragmented strategic areas of tourism recovery and development.

The processes of increasing competition are also caused by the global economic crisis. In such conditions, the market of tourist services should be constantly developed and improved, thus strengthening the position of Ukraine. This situation creates an increase in consumer demands for tourist products, so to meet the requirements of tourists it is necessary to constantly improve the quality and expand the range of tourist services. In addition, there is a close and interdependent connection between the development of the tourist services market in Ukraine and its regions. Improving the performance of an individual region and increasing its competitiveness will contribute to economic growth and strengthening of the economy, as the development of the state is closely linked to the development of the regions. We are convinced that the more developed and stable the country's economy is, the more stable the market of tourist services is.

The recent research and publications analysis shows that the scientific and theoretical basis of the study is the works of such scientists as V. Antonenko, A. Havryliuk, V. Horun, S. Kovalenko, M. Krachilova, O. Liubitseva, A. Marshall, O. Mezentseva, H. Parkhomenko, M. Porter, T. Tkachenko, V. Fedorenko, S. Khlopiak, L. Shulgina, V. Fedorenko and others. The analysis of works allows to carry out a systematic consideration of the vast majority of issues on the methodology of the model of strategic management in tourism for a tourist enterprise, analysis of the tourist services market and identify priorities for the tourism industry in Ukraine. However, the issue of elaborating an algorithm for the strategic development of the tourist services market, which is universal for the elaboration of regional programs for the development of tourist destinations, remains unexplored. This substantiates the relevance of this article.

The unsolved parts of the problem are clarification of the state, challenges and trends of strategic development of the tourist services market in Ukraine.

The purpose of the research is scientific and practical understanding and substantiation of the mechanism's implementation of strategic development of the tourism services market in Ukraine.

The scientific novelty of the article is to improve the theoretical and practical research of the methodology for identifying priority areas for the development of the tourism industry and developing an algorithm for the strategic development of the market of tourist services in Ukraine at the present stage.

Main research material

The tourist market, as a market of services, has its specific features that must be taken into account when organizing a tourism business. First, the tourist market is formed on the basis of services, and services are elusive (a tourist cannot try to buy, see or touch it when buying a tour), and are lost in time (profits from services that were not provided in a certain specific period of service are lost forever, flexible pricing and sales policy are needed). Secondly, when selling tourist products (tour, excursion or pre-booked hotel), there is a significant period between payment for the tourist product and its consumption. Reliability is important here. (i.e., guarantee of compliance with the expected quality of the purchased service and the actual level of service). Third, the tourism market is characterized by seasonal fluctuations in demand among tourists.

However, seasonality is different for each type of tourism. In addition, it determines the need for seasonal differentiation of prices for tourist services. Fourth, in the field of tourism, the quality largely depends on the specific performers i.e., service personnel (guides, guides, cooks, drivers, etc.) – employees of contact professions. Fifth, in the tourism market there is an objective territorial division between consumers and producers. The issue of advertising and promoting your product in the market of tourist services, informing tourists about interesting offers, cooperation with foreign partners, deepening international relations – all this is very important for the tourism business (Luo & Zhou, 2021; Li & Du, 2021). In order to succeed in this market, tourism businesses must be prepared not only to adapt quickly to the ever-changing needs of tourists but also to provide the highest quality tourism product that can even meet the needs of tourists.

A prerequisite for success Tourism development is the coherence of all strategic decisions at four levels: international, national, regional and at the level of individual enterprises in the field of government. However, a prerequisite for the successful development of tourism is the coherence of all strategic decisions at all levels.

Resort management needs to be settled. First of all, the main problems of the development of resorts in Ukraine are due to the lack of vertical management structure for a long time in the resort sector due to the failure to determine the authorized central executive body for resorts. It is for this purpose that the state should rethink the importance of resorts in the national system of health and recreation of the population, as well as the functions they perform. By changing the methodological approaches, the state will be able to develop new concepts for the development of resorts, spa services, where in the future will develop a program of strategic development of the tourism industry with the deepening specialization of resorts. Here it is necessary to take into account their uniqueness, and clearly define the right of ownership.

Tourism policy in Ukraine is implemented through state, regional and city tourism development programs. Documents adopted in recent years at various levels of government define the main goals of the tourism industry in Ukraine.

The analysis of scientific and practical literature (Antonenko & Khutkyi, 2018; Bartoshuk, 2011; Havryliuk, 2020; Porter, 2020) makes it possible to identify priority tasks for the development of the tourism industry, in accordance with the challenges of the time as shown in Figure1. The initial stages of these tasks indicate that this process can be very long, complex and demand a complete change in economic and social relations. System-forming factors, today, were formed in difficult conditions of the transition period with the lack of an effective economic model that can sufficiently ensure the coordination of the interests of all parties. Therefore, all changes in the system of the tourism industry should take place in order to increase not only the economic but also the social efficiency of the tourism services market.

We believe that to accelerate the development of tourism, it is necessary to implement the following measures:

1. Attracting finance to the tourism market. In Ukraine, the problem of attracting investments needs to be solved: public, private (domestic), or foreign (external). Our landscape, nature reserves, architectural and cultural heritage sites are attractive to tourists from various other countries.

2. Creating a relevant tourist brand of our country and improving the country's image at the international level. Unfortunately, journalists of foreign media do not promote Ukraine as a tourist destination.

Fig. 1. Priority tasks for the development of the tourism industry

[systematized by the authors on the basis of the scientific works' analysis Bartoshuk, 2011; Havryliuk, 2020; Porter, 2020; Luo & Zhou, 2021; Weaver, 2021]

3. Facilitation of holding various sports and cultural events of world scale in our country. Unfortunately, we are not represented at major tourism exhibitions.

4. Providing services at the appropriate level for demand entities with different income levels. Unfortunately, we have only 3% of international hotel chains, and this even though that the representatives of hotel chains indicate discomfort in their implementation in the Ukrainian market.

5. Formation of tourism for Ukraine with a targeted transition to European standards. It is important to note that the tool for implementing this strategy is the application of cluster models of development, development and implementation of training programs for tourism professionals. Equally important is the development of statutory documentation.

In tourism, there is always only one attempt to impress the guest, because the tourist service is produced and consumed at the same time. The tour operator, hotel or destination does not have time to correct mistakes, so it is important to do everything perfectly from the first time. Travel services have many symbolic and intangible components. Perceptions of the same product will be different, as it depends on the personal experience and expectations of each tourist. The tourist product is multifaceted and consists of many links – separate services. Each link is important and can change the impression of the whole product and even the whole destination.

In our opinion, first of all, one of the main tasks in the development of the tourist market of Ukraine is to define clear boundaries and scope of state intervention economic entities, attracting internal and external investors, establishing rules for the use of natural resources and regulating liability for their violation. The World Tourism Organization (UNWTO) (<https://www.unwto.org>) should develop a unified strategy for the tourism industry, which will include: planning for the development of the tourism industry, problem analysis; development of national and regional land use plans; taking into account the social consequences after the development of tourism. At the national level, the strategy can be developed by both national executive bodies and national legislatures.

We are talking about tourist attractiveness as a necessary condition for the popularity of the services market in Ukraine. The main factors that determine the tourist attractiveness of the regions include the overall image of the region; nature; climate and recreational resources; historical, cultural and spiritual values, political stability; infrastructure development; economic attractiveness. At the same time, the basis for the formation of popularity among tourists in the regions of Ukraine is an expansion of the network of tourist and recreational facilities and tourist information centres; formation of modern engineering, communal, the ecological infrastructure of tourist and recreational centres and resorts; development of a network of tourist facilities and improvement of tourist and recreational infrastructure; creation and promotion of new competitive tourist products and optimization of the market of tourist services.

Initially, from our standpoint, it is necessary to form tourist clusters, the essence of which is that in a certain territory are concentrated in order to create a tourist product. Enterprise groups share tourism resources, infrastructure, the labour market and complement each other. The interest of most countries in creating clusters is primarily due to two reasons: first, clusters help accelerate business development, and secondly,

increase the intensity of the emergence of new enterprises within them. According to world experience, in those countries where government programs have been created and financed in order to implement the cluster model, the economies of the respective industries have developed much more than where clusters were formed only at the expense of their potential. The formation of clusters requires the following prerequisites: proximity of markets, availability of specialized personnel, availability of suppliers, means of production and other resources, availability of specific local resources, scale effect in production, availability of infrastructure, low transaction costs and high-quality access to information. We are talking about tourist attractiveness as a necessary condition for the popularity of the services market in Ukraine. The main factors that determine the tourist attractiveness of the regions include the overall image of the region; nature; climate and recreational resources; historical, cultural and spiritual values, political stability; infrastructure development; economic attractiveness. At the same time, the basis for the formation of popularity among tourists in the regions of Ukraine is an expansion of the network of tourist and recreational facilities and tourist information centres; formation of modern engineering, communal, the ecological infrastructure of tourist and recreational centres and resorts; development of a network of tourist facilities and improvement of tourist and recreational infrastructure; creation and promotion of new competitive tourist products and optimization of the market of tourist services.

In addition to tourism clusters, it is necessary to create infrastructure and innovation clusters, they are formed around a system of guaranteed consumption of products and thus use the existing infrastructure, but with the use of fundamentally new technological solutions; innovation clusters, which are formed on the basis of a fundamentally new infrastructure that did not exist before. In these clusters, it is impossible to calculate the guaranteed demand for products and the formation of this cluster is possible only under state guarantees. Because such clusters also contribute to the optimization of the market of tourist services.

In the next direction of optimization of the tourist services market in Ukraine, we propose to consider the logistics of tourism. The use of logistics in the activities of a tourist enterprise makes it possible to significantly increase the profitability of the tourist business by reducing costs, as well as increasing the level of logistical coordination of all tourist services (Havryliuk, 2020; Moyle et al., 2020; Luo & Zhou, 2021). The logistical approach contributes to solving the problem of sustainable tourism development, preservation and restoration of the resource base of the industry; reduces (and ideally eliminates) the risks of environmental degradation, reduced quality of tourism services provided, threats to the health and safety of tourists, and therefore can serve as a basis for determining the strategy of sustainable tourism development in the country and its regions.

Another area of optimization is defined as innovative activities aimed at the use and commercialization of the results of research and development and determines the release of new competitive goods and services. Our research provided an opportunity to form useful innovations that will promote the development of the tourist market of Ukraine, in particular: the use of "smart home" technology in the hotel business, which allows more efficient use of all available resources. These trends were introduced in the United States when the Sustainable Suite Design Competition, organized by the

U.S., was first held in 2010. Green Building Council and ASID (American Association of Interior Designers). In our opinion, this technology allows to increase the efficiency and productivity of the hotel business management system and creates the pre-conditions for its competitiveness, because it allows you to combine safety, comfort and technical capabilities. According to the requirements of the time, it will be useful to more actively create electronic museum tours and virtual tours. So, anyone from anywhere in the world can visit the museum online and no matter how far it is. Thus, with the help of electronic tours of museums, you can attract new tourists, who after viewing the electronic museum begin to admire the culture, history, architecture of the country. This, in turn, encourages tourists to visit the country to get acquainted with it in more detail. Creation and popularization of mobile applications that will provide complete information on the tourist attractiveness of the regions of Ukraine and will satisfy all tourist requests.

Concerning regional strategies for tourism development and tourist destinations, it is important to note the regional authorities, Regional Coordinating Councils, which will be able to form on the basis of legislative and regulatory frameworks for tourism regional bylaws and regulations. And of course, every travel company should also have its own development strategy in the travel market with appropriate analysis and feedback. It should be noted that the main issue that needs to be addressed today is the establishment of coordination between the main participants in strategic planning, especially attention should be paid to local levels of government. For example, the differences between the strategy of development and increasing the competitiveness of the city from the city council and the strategy of tourism development of the region from the regional state administration. Here we should start cooperation at the level of goal setting, as well as joint activities of the region necessary to achieve them. The creation of a Regional Coordinating Council for Tourism will help to resolve this issue. Some companies in the tourism industry also need a philosophy of strategic development, but in addition to mastering strategic planning, they also need skills and abilities to adapt to sudden changes in strategy that may arise due to different situations in the country. Tourist entities should effectively monitor the effectiveness of strategies and make the necessary adjustments in case of deviations, clearly address the issues of identification, allocation of information, financial, human resources to implement the strategy.

Analysis of the model of strategic management gives grounds to conclude that a successful development strategy is based on almost simultaneous implementation of all stages with a strong connection of their individual components, which allows timely adjustments to management decisions and, consequently, increases the competitiveness of the market. It will be equally important to note that the qualification of employees in the tourism industry is strategically important for the development of the market of tourist services in Ukraine because today there is almost no appropriate system of training and retraining.

Strategic management in tourism for a tourist enterprise: the choice of direction – defining the goals and mission of the organization; analysis and diagnosis – analysis of the external and internal environment. (SWOT analysis); strategy formation – choice of direction, development of alternative strategies, choice of strategy; strategy imple-

mentation – implementation, evaluation and control. As the strategic management of a tourist destination is carried out by a much larger number of tourist infrastructure enterprises, they need coherence within the tourist cluster. They must be agreed upon within the strategic program of the region.

The model of the algorithm of strategic management of a tourist destination should take into account the situation in such geographical elements as the region in which the demand for a tourist product is formed; transit region visited by a tourist; the region that is the purpose of the visit – a tourist destination. It should be noted that since market participants are not only tourism enterprises, the interests and development of other participants in the tourism cluster should be taken into account in strategic plans at all levels (Bartoshuk, 2011; Weaver, 2021; Berbekova et al., 2021). Local executive and local governments should come together to coordinate strategic planning efforts without disagreement. The market of tourist services of Ukraine needs development and reconstruction. In order to prevent the collapse, state local governments should create programs for the development of the region, in which much attention should be paid to the search for new types of tourism.

Analysis of scientific, statistical and practical literature, we have the opportunity to identify the appropriate algorithm for developing a project for the development of competitiveness. The main components of the algorithm include: ascending provisions (legal basis and determination of the feasibility of the program; scope and purpose; assumptions) → initial conditions and problem definition (application process; analysis of project implementation prerequisites; problem definition) etc. (infrastructure; transport; accommodation; financing) → goals, objectives and priorities of the project (main goal and objectives; objectives; priorities; conditions for changing the goals, objectives and priorities of the program) → stages of project implementation → relationship of the program with other software solutions (marketing of the region (purpose and tasks of marketing; stages and measures of marketing) → financing → measures of the program → expected results and efficiency of the program → criteria of program implementation → organizational support and management (organization of management; coordination, control, monitoring of the Program implementation).

This algorithm can be used in the development of a regional program project for the development of mountain tourism, for example in the village Slavske, Lviv region, which is known for its available mountain resources. Analysis of the preconditions of the project for the development of mountain tourism in the village. Slavske has favourable natural conditions, has a convenient location for the development of competitive tourism; the relief of the Carpathians in the mountain resort of Slavske provides the development of certain winter sports; hotel infrastructure of Lviv is one of the best, but regional hotels are such as in the village. Slavske need innovation and modernization, Slavske is located at the intersection of important highways, Kyiv–Chop highway, but the distance from the regional centres is quite far and the current state of the connection needs significant improvement; analysis of injuries at a competitive ski resort requires expansion and improvement of medicine in accordance with international standards, assessment of energy and logistics proves the need for improvement, renewal and expansion; analysis of opportunities financing the development of a ski resort confirms the importance of attracting all possible investments and sources of

funding; Lviv is a famous tourist centre with a rich historical and cultural heritage, interesting traditions, developed gastronomic tourism, which is a positive factor in it. The main purpose of the village development project. Slavske as a competitive ski resort is to achieve worldwide recognition of the Lviv region as a centre of winter recreation by creating legal, social, economic and organizational conditions.

Slavske as a competitive ski resort: creating conditions for the strategic development of the region as an international centre of winter recreation; development of competitive sports infrastructure of the region with a focus on maximizing the use of all benefits after winter; significant improvement of the tourism industry of the region, creation of comfortable conditions for tourists in the region and a competitive resort Slavske as an integral part of the region with its tourist attractiveness (Antonenko & Khutkyi, 2018; Liubitseva, 2015). Coordination of actions on the realization of the regional development project of the competitive ski resort Slavske at the central, regional and local levels. In this context, a prerequisite for the implementation of the tasks of the program is the fulfilment of the obligations imposed on the state authorities and local governments of the Lviv region to implement the measures of the targeted state programs and this project.

The program should be designed for the long term. Successful implementation of the measures envisaged by the program is possible under the condition of its stable financing and annual implementation of the planned volume of tasks. It is planned to obtain the following socio-economic effects at the macro level: to provide conditions for winter recreation; to develop sports and accompanying tourist infrastructure; create appropriate conditions for training national teams; to increase the tourist attractiveness of Ukraine. At the regional level: to raise the development of Lviv region as a competitive tourist region by creating favourable conditions for winter recreation and sports; to improve living and recreation conditions in the region on the basis of the development of sports, tourism, transport infrastructure; to increase the tourist attractiveness of Lviv region, to open Lviv and the Ukrainian Carpathians to the world; create a powerful infrastructural potential for the development of all spheres of the social economy; to strengthen the market position of the region in tourism, to ensure its competitive advantages over the regions of neighbouring European countries specializing in winter tourism; to preserve the natural, historical and cultural heritage of Lviv region for future generations.

Therefore, all changes in the system of the tourism industry should take place in order to increase not only the economic but also the social efficiency of the market of tourist services. The activities of public authorities in the tourism industry should be in the direction of standardization of services, tourism product and increase the profitability of tourism infrastructure. Thus, the development of the tourist services market of Ukraine will be determined by the general tendencies of the world community development in the field of international tourism. Analyzing the current situation with the pandemic, to ensure this goal, it is necessary to introduce new ones that will contribute to the formation of a culture of travel. Project developers should focus on meeting the needs of consumers of tourism services. The main opponent with whom the struggle is being waged is the inconsistency of Ukraine's tourist offers with the usual ones for the consumer, who takes as an example the quality provision of tourist services abroad. After all, the tour-

ists who travel often will be carriers of information for other potential tourists. Coverage of a real positive holiday experience will help to form a desire to discover Ukraine.

Summarizing the above, it can be argued that to ensure a stable growth rate of the tourism industry it is necessary to (Antonenko & Khutkyi, 2018; Bartoshuk, 2011; Havryliuk, 2020; Porter, 2020): identify priority types of tourism for the regions; contribute to improving the safety of tourists; develop tourist infrastructure and transport links; simplify formalities; to create and sell tourist products and services that are in demand on the world market; develop and implement new technologies at a rapid pace, using digital tools. We believe that the tourism industry in Ukraine should become one of the strategic sectors of the economy, which will lead to further development of the state. The tourism industry of Ukraine is currently experiencing crucial moments on which the future of Ukrainian tourism will depend: tourism will become a significant source of revenue for the state budget or it will remain at the same level as it existed. All this is determined by the principles that will be the basis of the tourism development strategy. Thus, you can choose: to focus on foreign tourists or to pay more attention to the development of the domestic tourism process.

Thus, the main ways to optimize the tourism services market in Ukraine include infrastructure and innovation clusters); efficient logistics (logistics of recreational and tourist resources, logistics of the material and technical base of tourism, logistics of information infrastructure, logistics of transport infrastructure, logistics of excursion services, logistics of related services in tourism, logistics of production); innovative technologies ("smart home" technologies, creation of electronic museum tours and virtual tours, creation of mobile applications of tourist attractiveness of regions) and marketing (marketing of tourist image of the region, infrastructure marketing, marketing of sights (attractions), marketing support; staff marketing). Summarizing the above, we note that the market of tourist services in Ukraine will develop under conditions of tourism development, efficient use of available resources, compliance of service quality with international standards, stimulating innovation and investment in tourism in Ukraine, addressing sustainable tourism.

Conclusions

Thus, having conducted research, we can say that given the increasingly progressive development of international tourism and prospects for its development in Ukraine, the question of finding the optimal economic model for the development of the tourism industry remains relevant. We are convinced that further investment growth and large-scale joint actions will be able to expand the scope of services in the tourism industry of Ukraine, promote the development of tourism infrastructure and help realize today's potential for further growth. One of the prerequisites for the development of Ukraine's tourism industry by promoting domestic tourism products on the international market is the development of tourism strategies, implementation of these strategies and ensuring constant supervision, which will contribute to the dynamic development and competitiveness of domestic tourism companies.

The market of tourist services needs financial support for the development of travel agents and operators, improvement of staffing, support of the state-partner system,

the introduction of conditions for innovations in tourism and infrastructure development. In fact, a favourable state policy to support the tourism industry will be able to create a positive investment climate for the development of the tourism industry.

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СТРАТЕГІЧНІ ПЕРСПЕКТИВИ РОЗВИТКУ РИНКУ ТУРИСТИЧНИХ ПОСЛУГ В УКРАЇНІ

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Анотація

У статті проаналізовано теоретичні основи й особливості стратегічного розвитку ринку туристичних послуг в Україні. Осмислено та розкрито поняття туристичного ринку послуг. Виокремлено методологічний підхід стратегічного розвитку ринку туристичних послуг в Україні та специфіку відновлення після пандемії коронавірусу. Представлено й аргументовано пріоритетні завдання розвитку індустрії туризму в Україні. Узагальнено модель процесу стратегічного управління в туризмі для туристичного підприємства. Розроблено та обґрунтовано алгоритм розробки проєкту розвитку конкурентоспроможності ринку туристичних послуг України. Обґрунтовано висновок про те, що для забезпечення стабільних темпів росту індустрії туризму необхідно визначити пріоритетні види туризму для регіонів, сприяти покращенню безпеки туристів, розвивати туристичну інфраструктуру та транспортні зв'язки, спрощувати формальності, створювати та реалізовувати туристичні продукти й послуги, які мають попит на світовому ринку, розвивати та впроваджувати швидкими темпами нові технології, використовуючи digital-інструменти.

Ключові слова: індустрія туризму; ринок туристичних послуг; конкурентоспроможність; інновації; туристичні ресурси; туристичні послуги; стратегічний розвиток ринку туристичних послуг; маркетингові технології; ефективне управління

